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Influence of Parenting Styles on Mental Health of Undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of parenting styles on mental health of undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo. Parenting styles are recognised as influential in shaping the psychological and emotional development of children into adulthood. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised all undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo. A total of 400 undergraduates were selected using multistage sampling procedure. Data were collected with a structured questionnaire. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings reveals that authoritative parenting style was the most prevalent among undergraduates in the institution with overall weighted mean scores 3.40. It further revealed that higher percentage (52.5%) of the respondents reported poor mental health. Lastly, the study showed a significant relationship between parenting style and mental health ($r=.271$, p -value (Sig.) = .000) with authoritative parenting associated with more favorable mental health outcomes ($B = -.123$, $\beta = -.144$, $t = -2.682$, $p = .008$). The study concluded that authoritative style was the most prevalent among the study population. It further revealed that parenting styles significantly influence the mental health of undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo. Authoritative style was also showed to be mostly associated with positive mental health outcomes. The study recommends that parents should adopt balanced and supportive parenting approaches to promote emotional well-being among youths, and universities should provide support services to students exhibiting signs of distress, particularly those from neglectful or authoritarian homes.

Keywords: Parenting Style, Mental Health, Authoritative, Authoritarian, Permissive.

Introduction

The mental health of undergraduates has become a growing concern globally, with increasing rates of anxiety, depression, and emotional distress reported across higher education institutions. Mental health is seen as level of real well-being in which people understand their capacity, can cope with ordinary life pressures, can function productively and credibly, or can contribute to society. (Salari et al., 2020). According to World Health Organisation, WHO (2022), mental health is a state of mental well-being that enables people to cope with stresses of life, realise their abilities, learn well and work well, and contribute to their community. It is an integral component of health that underpins our individual and collective abilities to make decisions, build relationships and shape the world we live in. Mental health is also seen by Khan and Sabah (2020) as a dynamic condition of effective teamwork that enables people to use their skills in line with the society's widespread norms.

Mental health issues are prevalent among undergraduates in Nigerian (Ayinde et al., 2021; Falade, et al., 2020). Research shows that 58% of students experience depression, with varying severity levels (Dabana & Gobir, 2018). Similarly, studies indicate that mental health issues are common among undergraduates, with significant symptoms of depression, anxiety, and suicidal ideation (Oswalt, et al., 2020). The Healthy Minds Study found that over 60% of college students experienced at least one mental health issue in the 2020-2021 academic year (Lipson et al., 2022). Rweyemamu, et al. (2024), in their study on mental distress and associated factors among undergraduate students from a cross-sectional study at the University of Dodoma, Tanzania revealed that a significant proportion of the participants in the study have experienced

mental distress, indicating that undergraduate students are an at-risk population. According to their findings, about 52% reported to have experienced mental distress, and the associated factors were highlighted. This is because undergraduates are constantly subjected to multiple stressors that may arise from their academic pursuits or the transition from adolescence to adulthood (Ramón-Arбуés, et al., 2020, Hersi, et al. 2017). Furthermore, millions of children and adolescents experience behavioral issues, anxiety disorders, and depression, with significant implications for academic performance, social relationships, and economic outcomes (Agnafors et al., 2021; Klik et al., 2019; Ruban et al., 2013;).

One important factor contributing to mental health outcomes is parenting style but this factor is often overlooked. Parenting styles is seen as the process by which parents/guidians relate, interact, rear, react and direct children in the course of upbringing (Udo, et.al.2024). Parenting varies widely across families, with cultural backgrounds having a significant role in shaping family dynamics and child-rearing practices. Family is first focus that underpins educative foundations in it and some argue that the causes of incompatible behaviours in adolescents and young adults, further related to family factors, because human takes the first steps of socialization within the focus family (Akbari, 2015).

Nigeria, like many other African countries, has a rich cultural heritage and diverse parenting practices influenced by socio-economic factors, religious beliefs, and traditional norms. In Nigeria, parenting practices often reflect a blend of traditional and modern approaches, shaped by cultural values such as respect for authority, collectivism, and communal child-rearing (Olusakin & Gbadebo, 2016). However, rapid socio-economic changes, urbanization, and exposure to Western influences have led to shifts in parenting styles among Nigerian families (Adeyinka, 2018). These changes raise important questions about the implications of evolving parenting styles on the mental health of Nigerian undergraduates, who represent a vulnerable population undergoing significant developmental transitions. Researchers have categorized parenting styles into various groups, typically 3, 4, or 5 psychological constructs. Authoritarian, authoritative, permissive and neglectful parenting styles were focused in this study.

Authoritarian parents according to Terrence and Magda (2022), typically engage in a 1-way mode of communication where they establish strict rules that the child is expected to follow without question or negotiation. These rules are rarely explained, and children are expected to meet high standards without making mistakes. Errors are often met with punishment. Children raised by authoritarian parents often exhibit well-behaved behavior due to the consequences of misbehavior. Additionally, they tend to follow precise instructions more effectively to achieve their goals. However, this parenting style can also lead to higher levels of aggression, while children may also exhibit shyness, social ineptitude, and difficulty making their own decisions (Masud, Ahmad, Cho, and Fakhr, 2019). In Nigeria, authoritarian parenting is prevalent due to cultural norms that emphasize respect for authority and obedience. However, this style has been associated with increased psychological problems among Nigerian youths, including low self-esteem and higher rates of depressive symptoms (Akinsola, 2013).

Authoritative parenting style on the other hand is high on responsiveness and demandingness. These parents' value both instrumental and expressive attributes, for example, discipline conformity and freedom of self-will, yet they assume ultimate responsibility for the behaviour of their children (Hertherington & Parke 2022). Authoritative parenting is characterized by a close, nurturing relationship between parents and children. Parents set clear expectations and guidelines and explain the reasoning behind their disciplinary actions. They use disciplinary methods as a supportive tool rather than as punishment. This parenting style generally results in the healthiest outcomes for children but requires considerable patience and effort from both parties. In the Nigerian context, authoritative parenting has been linked to better academic performance and psychological well-being among adolescents (Okorodudu, 2010).

Permissive or Laissez-faire parents are defined as parents who give their children too much freedom, without interfering in the child's daily activities (Schaffer *et al.*, 2019). Permissive parents are high on responsiveness, but low on demandingness. They interact with their children in a passive manner, avoiding the use of the force when dealing with issues of discipline. (Okoro, 2018). Permissive parenting is characterized by high levels of responsiveness and warmth but low levels of demandingness and control. Parents adopting this style are indulgent and lenient, often allowing their children considerable freedom without setting clear boundaries or enforcing consistent rules. While permissive parenting can foster a close parent-child relationship and encourage independence, it may also have implications for children's mental health.

Neglectful parenting which is another parenting style also known as uninvolved parenting, is characterized by low levels of both responsiveness and demandingness. Parents who adopt this style are emotionally detached and disengaged from their children's lives, often failing to meet their basic physical and emotional needs. In Nigeria, neglectful parenting is often a result of socio-economic challenges that limit parents' ability to provide adequate support and supervision, leading to detrimental effects on youths' mental health (Adejuwon & Lawal, 2012). The absence of parental warmth and validation may lead children to internalize feelings of inadequacy and worthlessness. Neglectful parenting is associated with higher rates of mental health disorders among children, including depression, anxiety, and behavioral problems. The chronic stress

and emotional neglect experienced in neglectful households can contribute to the development of psychiatric disorders (Olusakin & Gbadebo, 2016).

Parenting style not only directly affects the mental health of students, but also has been shown to have a lasting influence on the development of students' behaviour, personality and other psychological characteristics. Understanding how these parenting styles influence the mental health of undergraduates is essential for devising effective interventions to promote their well-being.

Statement of the Problem

The mental health of undergraduates in Nigeria is a matter of increasing concern, due to the rising rates of psychological distress, anxiety, depression, and other mental health issues observed among this population. Studies indicate that mental health issues are common among undergraduates, with significant symptoms of depression, anxiety, and suicidal thoughts. While various factors contribute to these challenges, the family, especially parenting style, is foundational in early psychological development and coping mechanisms. Despite the cultural diversity within Nigerian society, there is a tendency for parenting practices to be influenced by traditional values, socio-economic status, and the rapid pace of modernization. These diverse parenting styles may have differential effects on the psychological well-being of undergraduate students, yet little empirical research has been conducted to examine these relationships within the Nigerian context. Moreover, while studies from Western contexts have identified associations between specific parenting styles (e.g., authoritative, authoritarian, permissive) and mental health outcomes in children and adolescents, it remains unclear whether these findings are generalizable to the Nigerian cultural context. Therefore, this study investigated the influence of parenting styles on mental health of undergraduates in Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to investigate parenting styles and its influence on mental health of undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo.

Specifically, the study aim to:

1. identify the prevalent parenting styles experienced by undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo.
2. assess the mental health status of undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo.
3. identify specific parenting style that is most strongly associated with positive mental health outcomes.
4. examine the relationship between parenting style and mental health of undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo.

Research Questions

1. What are the prevalent parenting styles among undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo.?
2. What is the mental health status of undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo.?
3. What specific parenting style is most strongly associated with positive mental health outcome?

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between parenting styles and the mental health of undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo.

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted for this study. Undergraduates at Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo. The study adopted a multistage sampling procedure to select 400 undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo as the sample size. First, the undergraduates were stratified based on faculties within the institution, each faculty was then further stratified by departments and academic level (100L-400L). Finally, a proportional number of students were selected from each subgroup using simple random sampling techniques to ensure representation. Structured questionnaire with three sections was used to collect data. Descriptive statistics (frequency count, percentage mean, and standard deviation) was used to describe the demographic data of the respondents and research question one and two, while inferential statistics (Regression and Analysis of variance) was used to analyse research question three and Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Data of the Respondents

Category	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	150	37.5
	Female	250	62.5
	Total	400	100.0
Age	Below 20years	180	45.0
	21 – 25years	180	45.0
	26 – 30years above	40	10.0
	Total	400	100.0
Religion	Christianity	270	67.5
	Islam	120	30.0
	Others	10	2.5
	Total	400	100.0
Level	Part I	170	42.5
	Part II	110	27.5
	Part III	60	15.0
	Part IV	60	15.0
	Total	400	100.0

Table 1 above showed that 150 (37.5%) of the respondents were male while 250 (62.5%) were female. It also showed that majority of the respondents are between age 25 and below while few are above 26years of age. It further showed that Christianity has higher percentage of respondents, followed by Islam, and other religion. Lastly, part 1 and 2 students have higher percentage of percentage compare to part 3 and 4.

Research Question One: What are the prevalent parenting styles among undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo?

Table 1: Prevalent of Parenting Styles among Undergraduates

S/N	Items	Mean	SD
Authoritarian Parenting Style			
1.	My parent(s) expected me to follow rules without question	3.05	.86
2.	Disobedience was punished harshly in my home	3.17	.92
3.	My parent(s) rarely allowed me to make decisions	2.77	.96
4.	My parent(s) were very strict and controlling	2.50	1.18
5.	I was disciplined without being given reasons	2.22	1.13
	Weighted Mean	2.74	
Authoritative Parenting Style			
1.	My parent(s) listened to my opinions before making decisions	3.45	.706
2.	My parent(s) explained the reasons behind rules	3.42	.543
3.	I was encouraged to express my feelings freely	3.42	.803
4.	My parent(s) consistently enforced rules but were also understanding	3.25	.581
5.	My parent(s) were warm and supportive	3.45	.836
	Weighted Mean	3.40	

Permissive Parenting Style

1. My parent(s) allowed me to do almost anything I wanted	2.52	.92
2. Rules were not strictly enforced in my home	2.72	1.00
3. My parent(s) rarely punished me	2.65	1.06
4. My parent(s) were more like friends than authority figures	3.10	.94
5. My parent(s) avoided confrontation with me	2.27	1.02

Weighted Mean

2.65

Neglectful Parenting Style

1. My parent(s) were mostly absent during my childhood	1.62	.85
2. My parent(s) did not show much interest in my education or activities	1.45	.80
3. I rarely had emotional support from my parent(s)	2.10	1.04
4. My parent(s) were too busy to care for my needs	1.60	.76
5. I often felt alone or unsupported at home	1.65	.88

Weighted Mean

1.68

The findings from the table 2 revealed that the authoritative parenting style is the most prevalent and dominant style among undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo. This is evidenced by overall weighted mean score of 3.40. Conversely, the authoritarian style showed moderate prevalence, with weighted mean scores 2.74. The permissive parenting style also showed moderate prevalence with weighted mean scores of 2.65. The neglectful parenting style had lowest prevalence with weighted mean scores of 1.68.

Research Question Two: What is the mental health status of undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo?

Table 3: Mental Health Status of Undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo

S/N	Items	Mean	SD
1.	I feel overwhelmed by academic or personal responsibilities	2.82	.97
2.	I find it difficult to sleep due to excessive worrying	2.62	1.11
3.	I feel sad or hopeless without a clear reason	2.50	1.02
4.	I have difficulty concentrating on tasks	2.52	1.00
5.	I feel anxious or restless in social situations	2.35	.96
6.	I feel worthless or experience low self-esteem	1.92	.96
7.	I avoid interacting with people, even friends or family.	2.32	1.21
8.	I often feel tired or drained even after rest	2.60	.97
9.	I feel confident and capable of handling challenges	3.02	1.01
10.	I find healthy ways to cope with stress	2.90	.99
11.	I feel emotionally stable most of the time	2.95	.89
12.	I feel optimistic about my future	3.32	1.01
Weighted Mean		2.65	

Rating: 1 = Never, 2 = Rarely, 3 = Sometimes 4 = Always

Results from table 3 showed a moderate level of mental health with overall weighted mean of 2.65. This indicated a balance between positive and negative outcomes, but still showing areas of concern.

Research Question Three: What specific parenting style is most strongly associated with positive mental outcome?

Table 4: Regression Analysis on Parenting Styles and Mental Health Outcome Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.379 ^a	.143	.135	.54032

a. Predictors: (Constant), NEGLECTFUL, AUTHORITATIVE, PERMISSIVE, AUTHORITARIAN

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	19.291	4	4.823	16.519	.000 ^b
Residual	115.318	395	.292		
Total	134.609	399			

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.114	.267		7.915	.000
Permissive	-.030	.067	-.021	-.449	.653
Authoritative	-.123	.046	-.144	-.2.682	.008
Authoritarian	.168	.045	.216	3.728	.000
Neglectful	.246	.049	.271	5.026	.000

The model summary and ANOVA table above revealed significant associations between parenting styles and mental health. ANOVA tests showed that each parenting style (authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and neglectful) significantly influenced students' mental health ($p < .005$). Looking at the coefficients, the neglectful parenting style emerged as the strongest positive predictor of poor mental health ($B = .246, \beta = .271, t = 5.026, p < .005$). The authoritarian style also showed a significant positive relationship ($B = .168, \beta = .216, t = 3.728, p < .005$), indicating it is another risk factor for poor mental health. In contrast, authoritative parenting demonstrated a protective effect ($B = -.123, \beta = -.144, t = -2.682, p = .008$), implying that higher levels of authoritative are associated with better mental health outcomes while permissive parenting did not have a statistically significant effect on mental health ($p = .653$)

Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between parenting styles and mental health of undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo

Table Five: Correlation Coefficient on Relationship Between Parenting Styles and Mental Health Correlations

	Parent Styles	Mental Health
Parent Styles Pearson Correlation	1	.271**
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
N	400	400
Parent Styles Pearson Correlation	.271**	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
N	400	400

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The data presents the result of a Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient. It indicated a statistically significant positive relationship between parenting styles and mental health ($r = .271, p\text{-value (Sig.)} = .000$) which is less than the

conventional level of significance (0.05). This indicates that the combination of the four parenting styles significantly predicts the mental health outcomes of the students. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between parenting styles and the mental health of undergraduates in the study population.

Discussion

The study examined parenting styles and its influence on mental health of undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo. Findings from table 1 showed the demographic data of respondents. Findings from table 2 showed the prevalent parenting styles among undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo. This is evidenced by overall weighted mean score of 3.40 on items reflecting warmth, responsiveness, explanation of rules, and encouragement of free emotional expression. Authoritative parenting, which combines high responsiveness with appropriate control, appears to be commonly practiced among respondents' families. Conversely, the authoritarian style showed moderate prevalence, with weighted mean scores 2.74. This suggests a notable proportion of students experienced strict discipline and high demands with limited responsiveness. The permissive parenting style also showed moderate prevalence with weighted mean scores of 2.65. The neglectful parenting style had lowest prevalence with weighted mean scores of 1.68, indicating that only a small percentage of students reported experiences of emotional neglect or parental absence. This revealed that each parent has a unique approach to interacting with and guiding their children, thereby shaping their morals, principles, and behavior. This finding is in agreement with the study of Olusakin & Gbadebo, 2016 which stated that, in Nigeria, parenting practices often reflect a blend of traditional and modern approaches, shaped by cultural values such as respect for authority, collectivism, and communal child-rearing.

Findings from table 3 which provided answer to research question two revealed a moderate level of mental health with overall weighted mean of 2.65. This indicated a balance between positive and negative outcomes, but still showing areas of concern. The findings indicate a considerable prevalence of psychological or emotional distress among students, despite the high presence of authoritative parenting, indicating that there are other possible contributing factors contributing to mental health outcome among undergraduates which may include academic stress, peer pressure, socioeconomic background, environmental factors etc. The study agreed with Rweyemamu, et al. (2024), in their study on mental distress and associated factors among undergraduate students from a cross-sectional study at the University of Dodoma, Tanzania which revealed that a significant proportion of the participants in the study have experienced mental distress, indicating that undergraduate students are an at-risk population. According to their findings, about 52% reported to have experienced mental distress, and the associated factors were highlighted. This is because undergraduates are constantly subjected to multiple stressors that may arise from their academic pursuits or the transition from adolescence to adulthood (Ramón-Arbués, et al., 2020, Hersi, et al. 2017).

Findings from table 4 revealed the specific parenting style mostly associated with positive mental health outcome. Statistical analyses revealed significant associations between parenting styles and mental health. ANOVA tests showed that each parenting style (authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and neglectful) significantly influenced students' mental health ($p < .005$). Regression analysis further explained 14.3% of the variance in mental health outcomes ($R^2 = .143$), demonstrating that parenting styles are moderately predictive of students' psychological well-being. The Adjusted R Square (0.135), which accounts for the number of predictors in the model, slightly reduces this figure, but it still supports a modest explanatory power. The standard error of the estimate (0.54032) shows the average distance that the observed values fall from the regression line.

Looking at the coefficients, the neglectful parenting style emerged as the strongest positive predictor of poor mental health ($B = .246$, $\beta = .271$, $t = 5.026$, $p < .005$), suggesting that higher neglectfulness is associated with worse mental health outcomes. The chronic stress and emotional neglect experienced in neglectful households can contribute to the development of psychiatric disorders (Olusakin & Gbadebo, 2016). The authoritarian style also showed a significant positive relationship ($B = .168$, $\beta = .216$, $t = 3.728$, $p < .005$), indicating it is another risk factor for poor mental health. Smetana, (2022) examines Parenting styles and adolescent development. the finding reveals that adolescents from authoritarian households reported lower self-esteem and higher levels of psychological distress. Chao, (2024) examines Beyond parental control: A model of Chinese parental influence on child behaviour. The research finding highlighted that authoritarian parenting negatively influenced children's mental health, particularly in emotional and behavioural adjustment. In contrast, authoritative parenting demonstrated a protective effect ($B = -.123$, $\beta = -.144$, $t = -2.682$, $p = .008$), implying that higher levels of authoritative are associated with better mental health outcomes. suggesting that students who experienced warmth and consistent guidance from parents were less likely to experience mental health challenges. This agreed with Baumrind (2018), who examined the influence of parenting style on adolescent competence and substance use. The study found that adolescents with authoritative parents exhibited higher levels of competence, better emotional regulation, and lower levels

of substance abuse. The supportive nature of authoritative parenting fosters resilience, contributing positively to mental health. Meanwhile, permissive parenting did not have a statistically significant effect on mental health ($p = .653$). Findings from table 4 showed a significant relationship between parenting styles and the mental health of undergraduates, confirming that the nature of parenting received has a measurable influence on students' psychological well-being. Parenting style has been shown to be one of the most important factors affecting student's mental health outcomes which is the focus of this study (Newman *et al.*, 2018). Parenting style not only directly affects the mental health of students, but also has been shown to have a lasting influence on the development of students' behaviour, personality and other psychological characteristics (Rohner and Britner, 2022; Rohner *et al.*, 2015; Huang *et al.*, 2018).

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that authoritative style was the most prevalent among the study population. The study further revealed that parenting styles significantly influence the mental health of undergraduates at Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo. Authoritative style was showed to be mostly associated with positive mental health outcomes. Authoritarian and neglectful parenting styles were shown to have negative effects on students' mental well-being, while permissive style show no significant relationship with mental health. These findings underscore the importance of family upbringing in shaping young adults' psychological resilience and emotional stability.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Stakeholders such as school counsellors and community leaders should organize workshops and sensitization programs to educate parents on the benefits of authoritative parenting, which balances discipline with empathy and support.
2. Universities should provide support services to students exhibiting signs of distress, particularly those from neglectful or authoritarian homes.
3. Future studies should explore other contributory factors to mental health outcomes, such as financial stress, academic workload, peer relationships, and exposure to trauma.

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